

Renewables Innovation

by Liam Kieran, ESB G&T

Energy for generations

Purpose:

To outline innovative options relevant to renewables grid integration in Ireland.

Agenda

0. Introduction
1. Why is better renewables integration necessary?
2. What grid support services can a windfarm provide?
3. What else can be done to minimise curtailment?
4. What innovative steps have been taken already?
 - 4.1 *Turlough Hill – Reducing curtailment through operational change*
 - 4.2 *Grousemount – Regulating voltage with full converter turbines*
 - 4.3 *Hybrid + Battery – Fast frequency response+*
5. Final thoughts

Who are we?

ESB G&T is a division of ESB that develops, constructs & operate generation plant in Ireland & UK.

By Q4, 2019, ESB will have 828MW of windfarms operational in Ireland & UK.

By Q4, 2030, ESB aim to increase our renewables generation portfolio by 2.7GW to 3.5GW.

Why is better renewables integration necessary?

Technology	Capacity Factor	MW for 1 TWh
Onshore Wind	31%	356
Offshore Wind	45%	253
Solar PV	11%	1000
Biomass	85%	134

Without renewables integration with grid, curtailment could destroy the business case to build.

Reason:

While developers must reflect curtailment impact in RESS bid prices, competition will limit bid increase possible

Is RES-E target partially dependent on better integration?

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	2020	2030 Low Demand Scenario	2030 High Demand Scenario
RES-E Target	40%	70%	70%
TWh R'd	11.2	24.5 (+13.3 TWh)	31.5 (+20.3 TWh)
MW R'd	3987	8,722 MW (+4735MW)	11,214 MW (+7227 MW)

What is key challenge to achieving 70% RES-E by 2030?

Based on predicted demand, developers must double or treble renewables generation in 10 years to satisfy 70% of electricity demand by 2030.

What is required for success?

According to IWEA, delivery of 70% RES-E target requires timely achievement of the following

1. Target
2. Planning
3. Route to Market
4. Grid Connections
5. Grid Capacity
6. Integration of renewables with grid with minimal curtailment *
7. Community Engagement / Support

Why does integration need to improve so much?

For integration to succeed, Eirgrid need to increase SNSP level to 95% by 2030.

What grid support services can a windfarm provide?

Voltage Support

Requirement: Help to maintain voltage within 5% of nominal values.

Support: Turbines with full converter turbines to supply MVAr outside grid code to regulate voltage better.

Frequency Regulation / Reserve

Requirement: Help to keep frequency at point of connection in range of 49.95 – 50.05 Hz

Support: Dialling back power to create reserve capability is possible, but uneconomic. It is better to add batteries to windfarms to provide response time of 100ms and power for 20 minutes.

Fault-ride Through Capabilities

Requirement: Keep windfarms connected during voltage drop & restore power production later quickly.

Support: With right ROCOF settings applied to turbines, windfarms can provide required fault ride-through capability.

Newest turbines can comply with 250ms power restoration requirement, after voltage returns to 90% of nominal value.

NB:

These grid support service complement those available from conventional synchronous generators.

What else can be done to minimise curtailment?

Challenge: When energy from wind/solar is high & demand is low, there will be a curtailment risk.

Solutions: More smart/switchable loads; Interconnection/Storage, Controllable Renewables Generation

Industry can help by

- 1) changing operating practices for existing assets (hydro, pumped storage, windfarms)
- 2) developing new renewables plant with better grid support services
- 3) developing hybrid renewables plant with batteries

What innovative steps have been taken already?

Turlough Hill – Reducing curtailment through operational change

Turlough Hill 292MW hydro pumped storage plant can go from standstill to full operation in 70 seconds.

By transferring water between two reservoirs at different elevations, it is possible to supply electricity during peak demand and store excess electricity during periods of low demand.

For details, please see link [1](#) & [2](#).

Turlough Hill–Reducing curtailment through operational change

Turlough Hill
Overall Generation Process

Operation cycle has been recently changed to include pumping during day to prevent wind curtailment. This requires more cycling plant, more low-load operation & more maintenance/inspection to protect plant.

To improve availability, we're running pilot programme with Akselos to move to condition-based monitoring. To improve operating efficiency at lower loads, we're investigating options to modify turbine blade runners.

Grousemount –Regulating voltage with full converter turbines

Challenge

Large amounts of cabling in South-West generating capacitive MVAr means voltage rises under low demand. There is little conventional synchronous generation connected here to control the voltage. Traditionally Eirgrid added stat-coms to vulnerable parts of network to deal with this issue.

Solution

Modern wind turbines can go beyond the grid code requirement to help Eirgrid to regulate system voltage, thus removing need for some stat-coms. Example=Grousemount windfarm

Requirement at PCC

Required Minimum Reactive Power Capability of Grousemount windfarm at the PCC (ie 110kV side of 110kV/33kV grid trafo at Coomataggart 110kV station)

Indicative Reactive Capability at 33V busbar

Significance

Traditionally, wind turbines did not support the grid, but now they can. They can produce MVARs at 0 MWs. Eirgrid can potentially use full reactive power capabilities of modern turbines to regulate voltage better. With this support, Eirgrid may be able to delay or avoid adding stat-coms to some capacitive networks.

Hybrid + Batteries – Fast Frequency Response+

In T-4 auction (2022-23), ESB won capacity market contracts to supply 154MW of battery banks on existing sites.

Using batteries to provide fast frequency response has these advantages

- Conventional generators provide reserve within 5-15 seconds. Batteries respond in 100ms.
- Batteries provide fast frequency response from 0MW, so wind doesn't need to provide operational reserve.
- Batteries provide other services too, including capturing power during dispatch down

Opportunity to develop hybrid sites (any combination of wind, solar, battery).

- Appropriate rulesets will increase opportunity.
- Consider international experience...

Hybrid + Batteries – Fast Frequency Response+

Hornsdale Wind + Battery , South Australia

- 100MW/129MWh battery plant was installed near 314MW Hornsdale windfarm in Australia in 2018
- Revenue streams came from reserve contract for 70MW + ancillary services from 30MW/storage.
- Revenue met 1/3 construction cost in 1 year of operation.

Final Thoughts

How can ESG&T help Eirgrid to maximise new renewables connections & minimise curtailment?

We can strive to develop renewables plant to provide both electricity & grid support services profitably.
We can collaborate to develop win-win solutions, test them on a small scale & replicate them elsewhere.
We can publicise successes to provide an example for others.